

NUMERICAL APPROACH FOR EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES OF WOOD COMPOSITES WITH PARTIAL RESIN COVERAGE OF STRANDS

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1 Introduction

Determining structural behaviour of strand-based wood composite products such as PSL (parallel strand lumber) beams is of interest to construction industry. Strand-based wood composites consist of partially covered orthotropic wood strands with small amount of resin. Unlike conventional fibre-reinforced composites, the resin content in strand-based wood composites is less than 10% by volume and strands are rectangular in shape.

The process involved in manufacturing of strand-based wood composite materials results in products that consist of voids in addition to resin and strands. The void content depends on the processing parameters and can affect the properties of these materials [1-3]. As shown in Fig.1(b), voids are mostly distributed between strands. In other words, strands are only partially covered with resin.

Based on homogenization techniques, a multi-scale modeling framework has recently been developed to take into account the effect of microstructure on macroscopic behaviour of strand-based wood composites [4, 5]. In this framework, the effective properties of a unit cell of the material at the lower scales are determined and used in the higher scales. In the previous studies strands were assumed to be fully covered with resin and perfectly bonded. In other words, the presence of voids in the microstructure was ignored.

Dai et al. [6] showed that resin distribution has a key effect on the final properties of oriented strand

boards. In this paper, we enhance the previously developed unit cell model (first step of the multi-scale approach in Gereke et al. [4]) by considering the partial coverage of strands.

Two strategies are presented for this purpose. First, voids are incorporated in the resin layers by replacing resin elements with void elements. Using this strategy the effects of size and spatial distribution of voids on effective properties of the material can be examined at a common range of resin contents of strand-based wood composite products.

Alternatively, and in order to improve computational efficiency, partial coverage is modelled using degraded elastic properties for the whole resin phase. The effective elastic properties using these two strategies are compared at different resin contents. Finally, the limitations and challenges involved in both strategies are discussed briefly.

2 Modeling Approach

2.1 Unit Cell of Fully Covered Strands

Fig. 1 represents a PSL beam and its cross-section. For modeling purposes, the material is idealized as a periodic assembly of rectangular strands with the same size and covered by a thin layer of resin with constant thickness (Fig. 2 (a)). Fig. 2 (b) shows the corresponding unit cell for strands that are fully covered with resin as well as the mesh using 8-noded linear brick elements, C3D8 in the

commercial finite element software, ABAQUS® [7] (Fig. 2 (c)).

To estimate the elastic properties, the stiffness tensor of the unit cell is computed using six elementary loadings (three uniaxial and three simple shear loadings) and periodic boundary conditions. Details of applying periodic boundary conditions on this unit cell of the material have been presented in [4].

2.2 Incorporation of Void Elements

In order to model partially bonded strands, voids are introduced in the resin phase by replacing some resin elements with void elements in the discretized unit cell of fully covered strands (see Fig. 3(a)). Resin elements are selected randomly and assigned very low elastic properties. A periodicity constraint is applied at the boundary of the unit cell using customized Python© scripts.

2.3 Resin with Degraded Properties

The effective properties of partially bonded strands may also be modeled using the unit cell of fully covered strand but with degraded resin properties (see Fig. 3(b)). This strategy is based on the analysis of two strands that are partially bonded together by a thin layer of resin with thickness, t_r (Fig. 4).

Interface parameters are defined as:

$$D_t = \frac{\sigma_t}{u_t} \quad (1)$$

$$D_n = \frac{\sigma_n}{u_n} \quad (2)$$

where σ_t and σ_n are tractions that are tangential and normal to the interface area, and u_t and u_n are the corresponding interface displacement jumps described by Hashin [8].

For fully covered strands with a thin layer of resin (with thickness t_r), D_t and D_n may be defined in terms of strand and resin properties (see Nairn [9]):

$$\frac{1}{D_t} = \left(\frac{1}{G_r} - \frac{1}{G_s} \right) t_r \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{1}{D_n} = \left(\frac{1}{E_r} - \frac{1}{E_s} \right) t_r \quad (4)$$

The interface parameters of a partially covered wood composite may now be deduced by introducing the

concept of resin area coverage of strands. For two partially bonded strands (Fig. 4), the tangential displacement jump, u_t , may be written as a function of the shear properties of the strand (G_s) and the resin (G_r), and the resin thickness as follows:

$$u_t = \gamma_r t_r - \gamma_s t_r = \left(\frac{\tau_r}{G_r} - \frac{\tau_s}{G_s} \right) t_r \quad (5)$$

where γ_r and γ_s are the resin and strand shear strains due to shear stresses in the resin and strand, respectively. By assuming that all the shear force from one strand is transferred uniformly to the other strand through the bond surface, Equation (5) may be written as:

$$u_t = \left(\frac{\tau_s \left(\frac{A_s}{A_r} \right)}{G_r} - \frac{\tau_s}{G_s} \right) t_r \quad (6)$$

where, A_s and A_r are the total strand area and the strand area covered with resin, respectively.

By defining Resin Area Coverage (R_a) as:

$$R_a = \frac{A_r}{A_s} \quad (7)$$

Equation (6) may be rewritten in terms of resin area coverage as:

$$u_t = \left(\frac{1}{R_a G_r} - \frac{1}{G_s} \right) \tau_s t_r = \frac{\tau_s}{D_t} \quad (8)$$

Therefore, the tangential interface parameter may be derived in terms of resin thickness, resin area coverage and the shear moduli of resin and strand as:

$$\frac{1}{D_t} = \left(\frac{1}{R_a G_r} - \frac{1}{G_s} \right) t_r \quad (9)$$

By comparing Equation (9) with Equation (3) for fully bonded strands, the behaviour of partially bonded strands in shear may be modelled as the behaviour of fully bonded strands with equivalent shear property defined as:

$$G_{r,deg} = R_a G_r \quad (10)$$

Using a similar approach, the normal interface parameter can also be derived in terms of resin thickness and Young's moduli of the resin and strand as follows:

$$\frac{I}{D_n} = \left(\frac{I}{R_a \cdot E_r} - \frac{I}{E_s} \right) t_r \quad (11)$$

Therefore, the behaviour of partially bonded strands in tension may be modelled using the concept of resin equivalent Young's modulus.

$$E_{r,deg} = R_a \cdot E_r \quad (12)$$

Equation (10) and (12) are used in a unit cell of fully covered strand to model partially covered strands.

The accuracy of this approach is evaluated in the next section by comparing the effective properties of this unit cell (i.e. unit cell of a fully covered strand with degraded resin properties) with the effective properties of the unit cell presented in Section 2.2.

Regardless of the strategy (void elements or degraded resin properties), the effective stiffness tensor of the unit cell for partially covered strands is estimated by solving six elementary boundary value problems described earlier in Section 2.1. The Young's and shear moduli as well as the three Poisson's ratios are determined from the inverse stiffness (compliance) tensor.

3 Results

The strand dimensions chosen for numerical simulations were taken from the experimental study conducted by Arwade et al. [10] and are given in Table 1. The elastic properties of the resin and the strand are taken from the literature [11]. The resin is assumed to be isotropic while the strand (Pine wood) is assumed to be orthotropic. Elastic properties of the resin and the wood strand are listed in Table 2.

In order to investigate the effect of strands' resin coverage, two cases are considered. In the first case (Case I), the thickness of the resin (t_r) that bonds the two adjacent strands is assumed to be constant. In other words, by increasing the amount of resin, only the resin area coverage (R_a) increases:

$$R_a = R_C / \left(1 - \frac{RTL}{(R+t_r)(T+t_r)(L+t_r)} \right) \quad (13)$$

In the above equation R_C is the resin content by volume and R , T and L are strand dimensions in the 3 directions. In the second case (Case II), which is more realistic, the resin thickness increases as more resin is applied (Fig. 6). According to the equation

proposed by Dai et al. [6], the resin area coverage can be expressed as a function of R_C as follows:

$$R_a = 1 - \exp \left(- \frac{\rho_s R R_C}{2 t_r (1 + MC) [\rho_r R_C + \rho_s (1 - R_C)]} \right) \quad (14)$$

In the above equation, MC is the wood strand moisture content (12% in normal condition), and ρ_s and ρ_r are densities of the strand and resin, respectively. According to Equation (14), resin area coverage increases nonlinearly with resin content.

Fig. 5 depicts variation of resin thickness (t_r) and resin area coverage (R_a) with resin content (R_C) in Case I (red lines) and Case II (blue lines). A schematic representation of these two cases is also shown in Fig. 6.

The effective longitudinal and transverse moduli of partially covered unit cells for both cases are given in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, respectively. In these figures, results from unit cells with incorporated void elements (Section 2.2) and unit cells with degraded resin properties (Section 2.3) are indicated by filled symbols (square for Case I and triangle for Case II) and hollow symbols (square for Case I and triangle for Case II), respectively. It should be noted that for unit cells with incorporated void elements in Case I, only the results for resin contents above 2% are presented. In fact, the resin area coverage in Case I is less than 20% at resin contents below 2% (see Fig. 5). For such very low resin area coverage, the relevance of finite element results obtained using void elements becomes questionable. However, the results obtained from degraded resin properties are valid due to more uniform stress and strain fields in the resin phase (see Fig. 9).

Regardless of the case considered (constant or variable resin thicknesses), very good agreement is observed between the results of the two strategies described in Sections 2.2 and 2.3.

Similarly, good agreements are found for estimated shear moduli and Poisson's ratios of the partially covered unit cells between both strategies (see Figs. 10 and 11). However, it should be noted that estimated shear properties for partially covered unit cell with incorporated void elements are more sensitive to mesh size than those with degraded resin properties. In order to be consistent in presentation

of the results, only converged values (with the same mesh size) are presented in Figs. 10 and 11. Mesh refinement has shown that the discrepancies between the results of the two strategies diminish when the mesh (for the case of the unit cell with incorporated void elements) is refined significantly. In other words, by refining the mesh, the numerical results obtained from unit cell with incorporated void elements become closer to those obtained from the unit cell with equivalent resin properties. This represents the computational efficiency of employing the degraded resin properties in estimating properties of wood composites with partially covered stands.

4 Discussions

Results presented in Section 3 show the validity of the numerical approach in estimating the effective elastic properties of partially covered strands using the degraded resin properties. However, as explained in Section 3, by decreasing the resin area coverage (i.e. more voids) to very low values, the relevance of finite element results become questionable. In these cases, comparison between the two strategies is meaningless due to low accuracy of finite elements results for the unit cell with incorporated void elements.

It is also worth mentioning that through refining the mesh in the first strategy, the size of void elements decreases. Thus, voids are distributed more homogeneously throughout the resin phase and the results approach the results of a unit cell with degraded resin properties. Maintaining the same void size distribution while refining the mesh (in the first strategy), is necessary to analyze the accuracy of the second strategy in more detail. Comparing the results of the two strategies in this case will better illustrate the validity range of the second strategy in terms of void size. This is the subject of future studies.

In order to investigate the sensitivity of the results to resin properties, unit cells with more compliant and stiffer resin properties were also analyzed. For this purpose, the Young's modulus of the resin was adjusted up or down by an order of magnitude (factor of 10). Figs. 12 - 15 show the results for the more compliant resin properties while Figs. 16 - 19 show the corresponding results when the stiffer resin properties are used. In both cases (unit cells with

more compliant and stiffer resin properties), good agreements were observed between the results of the two strategies (errors less than 5%). Therefore, it can be concluded that the degraded resin properties can be employed effectively in the numerical approach regardless of the type of resin used in manufacturing of strand-based wood composite products.

5 Conclusions

The results presented in this paper show that the effective properties of partially covered strand-based wood composites can be estimated both efficiently and accurately through degraded resin properties arising from the concept of interface parameters [1, 2]. This strategy can be employed within the multi-scale modelling framework previously developed for predicting the structural behaviour of strand-based wood composites [3]. Moreover, the equations presented in Section 2.3 for degraded resin properties can be used later in developing physically based analytical micromechanical models for strand-based wood composites with partial coverage of strands [12].

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Fig. 1. (a) A PSL beam. (b) Cross-section of a PSL beam.

Fig. 2. Unit cell definition and FE discretization.

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Fig. 3. Discretized unit cell: (a) with incorporated void elements, and (b) with degraded resin properties. Resin area coverage in both unit cells is 70%.

Fig. 4. Two partially bonded strands.

Fig. 5. Relationships among resin thickness, resin area coverage and resin content for the two cases considered (Case I and Case II).

Fig. 6. Schematic showing resin area coverage with increasing resin content: (a) Case I – constant resin thickness, and (b) Case II – variable resin thickness. The initial resin content in both cases is the same.

Fig. 7. Effect of resin content on the longitudinal Young's modulus. Finite element results using void elements and degraded resin properties are shown with filled and hollow symbols, respectively.

Fig. 8. Effect of resin content on the transverse Young's modulus. Finite element results using void elements and degraded resin properties are shown with filled and hollow symbols, respectively.

Fig. 9. Predicted unit cell deformation under tension in the longitudinal direction using: (a) void elements, and (b) degraded resin properties. Case I, $R_c = 1\%$ and resin area coverage is 10% in both figures.

Fig. 10. Effect of resin content on the shear modulus. Finite element results using void elements and degraded resin properties are shown with filled and hollow symbols, respectively.

Fig. 11. Effect of resin content on the Poisson's ratio. Finite element results using void elements and degraded resin properties are shown with filled and hollow symbols, respectively.

Fig. 12. Longitudinal Young's modulus with more compliant resin. Finite element results using void elements and degraded resin properties are shown with filled and hollow symbols, respectively.

Fig. 13. Transverse Young's moduli with more compliant resin. Finite element results using void elements and degraded resin properties are shown with filled and hollow symbols, respectively.

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Fig. 14. Shear moduli with more compliant resin. Finite element results using void elements and degraded resin properties are shown with filled and hollow symbols, respectively.

Fig. 17. Transverse Young's moduli with stiffer resin. Finite element results using void elements and degraded resin properties are shown with filled and hollow symbols, respectively.

Fig. 15. Poisson's ratios with more compliant resin. Finite element results using void elements and degraded resin properties are shown with filled and hollow symbols, respectively.

Fig. 18. Shear moduli with stiffer resin. Finite element results using void elements and degraded resin properties are shown with filled and hollow symbols, respectively.

Fig. 16. Longitudinal Young's modulus with stiffer resin. Finite element results using void elements and degraded resin properties are shown with filled and hollow symbols, respectively.

Fig. 19. Poisson's ratios with stiffer resin. Finite element results using void elements and degraded resin properties are shown with filled and hollow symbols, respectively.

Table 1. Strand dimensions given in Arwade et al. [10]

Strand Dimension (mm)		
Length (<i>L</i>)	Width (<i>T</i>)	Thickness (<i>R</i>)
600	13	5

Table 2. Elastic properties of constituents

		Wood Strand (Pine)	Resin (PF)
Young's Modulus (GPa)	E_1	13	
	E_2	1.393	7.6
	E_3	0.856	
Shear Modulus (GPa)	G_{12}	0.991	
	G_{13}	0.909	2.92
	G_{23}	0.162	
Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	0.467	
	ν_{13}	0.456	0.3
	ν_{23}	0.488	

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